

Use Of Dictogloss Technique To Improve Writing Skill Of Undergraduate Students In ELT Classroom

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: November 01, 2022</p> <p>Accepted: February 02, 2023</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Writing, English Language, Students', Teacher Training</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7601138</p>	<p><i>Writing skills are declared to be the most complex as well as neglected among other English language skills (Alsamadani, 2022). The focus of current study is to investigate the effectiveness of an innovative teaching technique i.e. dictogloss to teach writing skills to ESL students. The nature of this study is quantitative. To fulfill the objectives of the study and investigate the impact of dictogloss on students' writing skills a quasi-experimental study was designed. Pre-tests and post-test of both the experimental and control groups were conducted and analyzed by conducting t-test. Data related to students' perceptions and attitudes towards learning writing skills through dictogloss was collected by using a closed ended questionnaire. The data was analyzed statistically. The correlation between understanding the steps of dictogloss and students' ability to use new vocabulary items in their written work was found using Pearson correlation through SPSS software. The results depicted that dictogloss is an effective teaching strategy to teach writing skills to the students. Moreover, the students found it easy, engaging, useful and showed their likelihood to continue learning through dictogloss. This research will be beneficial for ESL students, as well as teachers. Further, it will enlighten teacher trainers as well as educational administrators to organize teacher training session in order to equip ELT teachers to use innovative, interactive and integrated ELT teaching techniques such as dictogloss in class. This study strongly recommends the use of dictogloss in ELT class because it integrates and enhances all four-language skill of the students.</i></p>

Introduction

English has become Lingua Franca (Haidar & Fang, 2019b). English has not only been used as an official language in Pakistan but is also said to be a language that helps people gain a prestigious and high social status (Haidar & Manan, 2021). Nonetheless, English plays a controversial and divisive role in society as the elite class is privileged enough to avail ample English language practice opportunities in their social circle. Due to ample language practice opportunities, they become proficient English language users. On the other hand, there are less privileged members of society in terms of their English language learning and practice opportunities. Lack of language learning opportunities is a prominent factor behind their weak English skills. Consequently, they must survive with underdeveloped English language skills (Haidar & Fang, 2019a; Samiullah & Haider, 2022).

English is the second and official language of Pakistan. It has also been used as the medium of instruction in the universities of Pakistan. According to the EMI policy of Higher Education in Pakistan, both public and private universities are bound to practice English as the medium of instruction (Mansoor, 2004). Therefore, English is the language of academics not only in many other countries but in Pakistan as well.

Learning English language skills includes the development of four essential skills, i.e. listening, speaking, reading and writing. Many students from different linguistic backgrounds have soft English language skills (Mahboob, 2017; Mansoor, 2004; Samiullah & Haider, 2022). Writing, as one of the productive skills, is the most challenging one compared to the other language skills (Alsamadani, 2022), and they are one of the neglected skills in the early stages in Pakistan. Writing skills in the English language are more important as it directly influences the overall performance of the students (Samiullah & Haider, 2022) because the examination system in Pakistan is also based on written examination. Due to the examination system.

Among the basic language skills, writing being one of the productive skills, is the most crucial one. These days, writing has become the most challenging skill in the English language classroom because it requires a good mastery of all four language skills (Alsamadani, 2022). The best way to teach writing is through reading. The more the student reads, the quicker he becomes a skilful writer. With the advancement of social media, writing has become an inevitable tool for written communication (Alsamadani, 2022). This has made the role of EFL teachers even more crucial. Now the teachers not only have to focus on the main content of the lessons in

an EFL class, but they become more conscious about the development of the writing skills of their students. It is the time for teachers to have a deep insight into their teaching methodologies, especially while teaching writing skills to ESL students. Teachers are ready to transform their teaching methodologies. They are more inclined to replace their traditional teaching methodologies with innovative ways of teaching writing skills to ESL students. ESL teachers are working hard to make their classes more interactive and exciting for the students by incorporating student-centred activities (Alsamadani, 2022).

It has been observed that both listening and writing skills should be addressed while teaching English in Pakistani. More focus has been given to reading skills and replicating the crammed material during the written examination. Moreover, students' primary English language skills are neither developed at any level nor assessed during the examination. The teaching is also primarily based on traditional methodology, and the students are prepared to attempt the exam papers based on content-based teaching and learning in an ESL context. Keeping in view the current status of the weak writing skills of students in Pakistan, the present study has been designed to introduce an innovative teaching technique: developing the writing skills of students by using the dictogloss technique. The literature review further depicts that dictogloss has rarely been used to enhance the writing skills of ESL students in the Pakistani context. The purpose of the present study is to enlighten English language teachers regarding the application and effectiveness of dictogloss for developing the writing skills of ESL students. The study also uncovers the perceptions and attitudes of students regarding learning writing skills through dictogloss as well as the underpinning factors behind dictogloss being one of the effective techniques used to enhance the writing skills of students.

1. Research Objectives

1. To find out the effectiveness of dictogloss strategy to improve descriptive writing skills undergraduate students.
2. To explore the perceptions and attitudes of undergraduate students regarding the use of dictogloss strategy.
3. To find out whether there is any correlation between comprehending the steps of dictogloss and students' ability to use vocabulary items in their writings.

4. Literature Review

“The term “Dictogloss” comes from two words, namely “dictation” and “gloss”. Dictation roughly means putting of the words expressed by someone into paper which is done by somebody else, while gloss explanation, commentary, translation” (ibid). According to T. Saifulamri “Dictogloss is an integrated skill technique for language learning in which students work together to create a reconstructed version of text read to them by their teacher” (as cited in Yanti, 2018). In this teaching technique, the learners listen to the text read by the teacher at an appropriate speed and write down maximum words they can while listening. During dictogloss, students are allowed to discuss in groups and produce a new piece of writing by utilizing the words and phrases that they have noted down from during listening. This technique is similar to the traditional technique called dictation (Nunan, 2003) in which the words and the text was expected to be written by the learners merely by listening to the text carefully. In dictation, the individuals were expected to write a text accurately, however, dictogloss demands the learners to produce a text collaboratively with the support of their group fellows. The learners listen to the text, note down words and phrases and interact with each other in small groups and produce a text as a team work. There is a perception that by utilizing dictogloss, the students become aware of their own strengths and weaknesses regarding the use of English language (Nunan, 2003). It further encourages the students to reflect upon their writing skills (Wajnryb, 1990) and learn English by critically analyzing each other's mistakes and guiding one another in doing corrections. Dictogloss has been introduced by Wajnryb in 1990 as an innovative technique opposite to the traditional way of teaching grammar.

He proposed dictogloss to be conducted in four important steps listed below:

1. Warm-up: The students get familiar with the topic and practice a few vocabulary items.
2. Dictation: The teacher reads the passage loudly at an appropriate speed. Usually the students listen to the passage twice. At first, the students only listen to the text. On the second time they listen to the text and make some notes.
3. Reconstruction: The students work together in small groups and work collaboratively to produce a new piece of writing.
4. Analysis and Correction: At this stage, the students compare their new version of the text with the original text and analyze it to make important corrections through discussion.

4.1 Strengths of Dictogloss Teaching Technique

A number of benefits related to employing dictogloss in writing class have been highlighted by scholars.

4.1.1 Dictogloss as an Engaging and Interactive Teaching Technique

Dictogloss is most appropriate to conduct an interactive and engaging ELT class because it promotes class discussions and encourages students to speak in the target language, enabling them to enhance their spoken as well as argumentative abilities. Such kind of language learning environment that is comprised of individual as well as group activities provides a healthy language learning platform to the students where they can learn from each other. (Younis, Bataineh & Yarmouk, 2016).

4.1.2 Integration of four skills

Most of the ESL teachers tend to focus on a single or two skills, vocabulary or system items by utilizing old communicative method of teaching, PPP (Presentation, Practice, Production) or TTT (Test-Teach-Test). The ESL instructors do not dare to practice a variety of approaches such as Silent Way, TBLT (Task Based Language Teaching), Dictogloss etc. Nevertheless, the innovative teaching approach called dictogloss encourages the ESL teacher to integrate all four language skills as well as their systems in their classrooms (Jose, 2022). Many times, the ESL teachers often fail to integrate all four skills in the class, however, dictogloss fosters the integration of all four skills specifically by enabling learners to produce a written text with more grammatical accuracy (Kurtaj, 2021) in cooperation with other skills. i.e listening, speaking and reading (Jose, 2022).

4.1.3 Learning from their Peers

Dictogloss provides a chance to the learners to learn language from each other while working in groups. Each student in the group has different level of English language proficiency. Students correct each other's mistakes and provide feedback on the work of their fellows which helps them to get familiar with their own strengths and weaknesses in writing and encourages them to produce an improved version of their work. Furthermore, working in groups also helps them to reduce their language anxiety associated with writing skills. In addition to the development of writing skills, dictogloss also enhances other skills of students, for example listening skills (Vasiljevic, 2010).

4.1.4 Team Work

Another advantage of dictogloss is that it aids learners to analyze and produce written text while working in collaboration with fellow students. It encourages students to write meaningful text instead of just practicing writing skills in segregation. It motivates students to focus on grammar, motivates them to utilize their critical thinking skills and enhance confidence to use English language. As dictogloss is one of the student-centered ways of teaching and learning, therefore the students become active learners and learn more effectively in ESL classroom (Smith, 2012).

According to Lim and Jacobs (2001) participating in small group activities, learning collaboratively from their peers and by producing a text in groups, the students also gain inner satisfaction and happiness. All this cumulatively has a positive impact on students' performance and it fosters the whole process of second language acquisition.

4.1.5 Previous Research Studies Conducted on Dictogloss

In past years, a number of researchers have conducted experimental studies in order to test the effectiveness of dictogloss in improving only writing skills of students (Younis, Bataineh & Yarmouk, 2016) and writing skills integrated with other aspects such as listening comprehension (Sani, Inderawati & Vianty, 2016), students' attitudes regarding use of dictogloss (Alsamadani, 2022) learning multiword items through the use of dictation and dictogloss (Yu, Boers, Tremblay, 2022).

Younis, Bataineh & Yarmouk (2016) initiated an experimental study on 20 Jordanian EFL teachers to investigate their written instructions on 96 students studying at 10th grade level. They studied the effectiveness of teachers' teaching on students' performance in writing class. They investigated the impact of a complete teacher training program designed on dictogloss technique. The results of the study revealed that dictogloss enhanced the level of teachers' classroom instructions on three aspects (preparation and planning, procedures used in dictogloss, and assessment). The results further depicted the positive impact of dictogloss on overall development of students' writing skills.

Sani, Inderawati & Vianty (2016) also conducted an experimental study on 10th grade Indonesian students by using podcasts in dictogloss technique. The study investigated the impact of dictogloss on listening comprehension and writing skills of students. The findings revealed that there was a significant improvement in the listening comprehension as well as writing skills of students. In order to foster the effectiveness of dictogloss, he further suggested that ESL teacher should consider the English language proficiency of students while making their groups. The students should rather be grouped in such a manner that the proficient students can help weak students to improve their English language skills.

Matthew Y. Schaefer (2017) used video dictogloss in English discussion class (EDC). In this research, the students were asked to note down phrases from the teacher created videos and perform particular language functions in small groups by using them to take part in in-class topic-based class discussions. The study focused on introducing certain topics to the students and encouraging them to use phrases to communicate in target

language. The study was based on Noticing Hypothesis which sustains that the students are more inclined to acquire certain language items if they are engaged in such a manner that they focus on communicative use of language items in context. This was a task-based activity in which the students produced a written text in groups after watching teacher created videos followed by discussions on different topics.

Jose (2022) pointed out that ESL teachers mainly rely on traditional method of teaching along with communicative approach, however, they do not seem to be confident enough to use a variety of teaching methodologies in their classrooms. ESL teachers must break this monotony and should rather try to incorporate innovative teaching methods in classrooms (Younis, Bataineh & Yarmouk, 2016). Jose (2022) further advised EFL teachers to utilize eclectic teaching approach which would not only help them to achieve their lesson objectives more effectively but also enable them to gain professional expertise by conducting different kinds of activities with their students. Moreover, he encourages teachers to practice an integrated teaching technique i.e. Dictogloss in ESL classrooms. He conducted a qualitative experimental study in Oman, on pre-intermediate level adult learners of various nationalities. The research focused on using dictogloss and lesson reflections in ESL context. The results showed that dictogloss has positive impact on students' writing skills and development of self-reflective abilities in students.

Watching English videos helps to develop writing skills of students (Samiullah & Haider, 2022). YouTube is one of the affordable and effective web-based multimedia learning tool, easy to be integrated in ESL classroom. A variety of ICTs such as smartphones, internet, gadgets, websites etc can be used to enhance English language skills of L2 learners (Alobaid, 2022).

Joe (2022) suggested a dire need of research studies on students of different age levels, having different cultural backgrounds in Arabic context as well as in other parts of the world. On the other hand, Younis, Bataineh & Yarmouk (2016) also generously accepted the positive impacts of dictogloss. They sustained that dictogloss not only has a significant effect on students' writing skills but it also helps teachers enhance their teaching skills. Therefore, it is advised that Jordanian EFL teachers must be trained to utilize dictogloss strategy in their ESL classes.

Keeping in mind that both listening and writing skills have been ignored in EFL classrooms all grade levels. Therefore, the students in Pakistan have underdeveloped writing skills even then they reach at university level. Poor writing skills are badly deteriorating the over-all performance of students. The literature review further reveals that dictogloss has been rarely used to enhance writing skills of the ESL students in Pakistani context and this area is under-research. Therefore, there is a dire need to conduct this research in this area in order to enlighten ESL teachers of Pakistan regarding the application and effectiveness of dictogloss to develop writing skills of ESL students. This research also explores the perceptions and attitudes of students regarding learning writing skills through dictogloss as well as the underpinning factors behind dictogloss as a successful teaching technique to be used in writing class.

Methodology

The participants of the current study were 41 undergraduate students of BS Criminology semester two and three at The University of Lahore enrolled in Fall semester, 2022. In order to conduct this quasi-experimental study similar to Alsamadani (2022) unbiased and with reliability, the students were randomly selected and divided into two groups: experimental group (20 students) and control group (21 students) following nonequivalent group design technique. The aim of teaching both the groups was to enhance their writing skills. The experimental group was taught by using dictogloss technique whereas the control group was taught through the regular teaching methodology. The classes were conducted for fifteen weeks, two hours each week, totaling 30 hours. Both the groups were taught writing skills twice a week one hour each class. The participants of this study were of mixed gender both male and female students of ages between 18-20 years. Medium of instruction used in both the classes was English. The podcasts were randomly selected by the researcher from <http://www.bbc.co.uk/learningenglish/english/features/6-minute-english>. Each podcast lasts for six minutes. The topics of the podcasts were relevant to everyday life of the students. This further enabled the students to grasp the concept, to note down the words and phrases that they listened through the audio and utilize them in their writing. In order to assess the writing tests of students, the researcher used analytic scale adapted from test scoring rubrics proposed by Brown (2003), the test was scored in terms of content, organization, vocabulary, punctuation/mechanics/spellings and grammar. To check the validity of the writing test, the researcher invited two English language teachers to examine the instruments, the suggestions and the recommendations of the English language teachers were considered to produce the final version of the test. In order to analyze the reliability of the test, the instruments were tested on 20 students who were not the participants of the research. The same test was repeated and administered after three weeks on the same group and the results showed high reliability score of .84. A quantitative questionnaire comprised of ten closed ended questions was adapted from Yanti (2018) in order to collect data related to the perceptions and attitudes of students towards dictogloss teaching technique. The questionnaire was distributed at the end of research, in the last class of experimental group after they finished their post-test. The questionnaire explored the interest and

feelings of students regarding the entire teaching learning process using dictogloss, listening to podcasts and its effectiveness to enable them to produce a written text in English. A panel of 10 English language teachers checked the validity of the questionnaire and their feedback was recorded to produce the final version of the questionnaire. The purpose of the questionnaires was explained to the students first and then they were distributed among all the twenty students of experimental group. The questionnaire was collected back after being filled up by the students. All the students filled and returned the questionnaires with responsibility. Their responses collected through the research questionnaire were recorded. The data was analyzed statistically using SPSS software. The findings were presented in the form of tables. The aim of the questionnaire was to obtain valid data related to the attitudes and perceptions of students while learning to write through dictogloss.

The correlation between understanding the steps used in dictogloss(Q.3) and students' ability to use new vocabulary items introduced through dictogloss in their writings(Q.5) was analyzed by finding Pearson correlation by using SPSS software. The results were presented in the form of table.

Procedure Followed for Dictogloss Activity with Experimental Group

Following steps were followed to practice dictogloss activity with experimental group.

1. The students were asked to get into small groups of three to four members.
2. The students were given instructions about dictogloss activity.
3. They were asked to comprehend the podcast while listening to it.
4. They were asked to focus on the usage of the words and phrases as they would listen to the podcast.
5. The topic of the podcast was introduced to the students and first a small group discussion was held.
6. The teacher initiated an open discussion about the topic and students contributed well.
7. The audio was played and the students listened to it carefully.
8. The students were asked to note down as many words and phrases they can while listening to the audio for the first time.
9. The audio was played for the second time and students were again asked to listen and note down as many words and phrases they can.
10. The audio was repeated for the third time according to students' requirement.
11. A small activity was held in which the students shared their work with the other members of the group.
12. The students increased their list with the help of other group fellows.
13. The students were asked to construct a paragraph individually by utilizing the words and phrases they have noted down.
14. The students compared their work with other group members and did peer checking.
15. They guided each other to find out the mistakes and do corrections.
16. Each student then produced the final version of their writing.
17. One member from each group presented their work orally in front of class.
18. The teacher noted down overall mistakes of the students and provided collective feedback in the last part of the class time.
19. Writing Samples of the students were collected, graded and detailed feedback was provided to the students.

The Procedure Followed for Teaching Control Group

1. The teacher introduced the topic to the class.
2. Open discussion was held in class.
3. The students were asked to write an essay on the given topic individually.
4. No audio was played.
5. The students were not provided with any vocabulary items.
6. Some students were invited to give oral presentation of their work in class.
7. The teacher provided overall feedback to the students.
8. Writing Samples of the students were collected and graded.

5. Data Analysis and Interpretation

5.1 Analysis of Students' Questionnaire

Number of respondents according to their Responses and Percentages

Table 1

No	Statements	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
1	Dictogloss motivates me to write in English.	71% (15)	23% (5)			5% (1)
2	Dictogloss helps me to write descriptive texts in	57% (12)	38%		5% (1)	

	English.					
3	The steps in dictogloss are understandable.	33% (7)	57% (12)	5% (1)	5% (1)	
4	I can understand the vocabulary items from the podcast during dictogloss.	71% (15)	29%			
5	I can use the words and phrases to do descriptive writing through dictogloss.	57% (12)	29 (6)		10% (2)	5% (1)
6	Dictogloss makes the entire writing process very easy.	38% (8)	48% (10)	5% (1)	5% (1)	5% (1)
7	Dictogloss helps me to understand the structure of descriptive writing.	33% (7)	48% (10)	15%	5% (1)	
8	Dictogloss has me helped to improve my confidence while performing written task.	61% (13)	33% (7)		5% (1)	
9	The activities in dictogloss is fun.	95% (20)	5% (1)			
10	I want to continue learning through dictogloss.	90% (19)	10% (2)			

With reference to the responses registered by the students of experimental group for Q1, most of the students strongly agree (71%) and some (23%) agree that dictogloss plays a vital role in motivating them to write in English whereas only a little number of students i.e 5% reported that use of dictogloss doesn't play any significant role in motivating him to write in English. In response to Q2. More than half of the students strongly agreed (57%) and some (38%) admitted that use of dictogloss technique to teach them writing skills in fact helped them to produce descriptive text in English. However, only an insignificant number of students i.e 5% disagreed with the statement. According to the responses given by students for Q.3, most of the students (57%) agree and some students (33%) strongly agree that steps used in dictogloss to teach writing skills to the students are easy to comprehend. On the other hand, 5% students i.e one student showed reluctance to register his response whereas one student (5%) depicted his disagreement with the statement. For Q.4, most of the students (71%) strongly agreed and some students (29%) agreed that they were fully able to understand the vocabulary items introduced in the podcast. However, no one complained any difficulty regarding comprehending vocabulary items from podcast. So far as Q.5 is concerned, more than half of the students (57%) strongly agreed and (29%) gave positive response that they were able to use words and phrases introduced through the podcasts in their descriptive writing. Only 10% students disagreed and 5% strongly disagreed with the statement and complained that they were unable to use vocabulary item introduced through podcast in their descriptive writing. In response to Q.6, Most of the students (48%) mentioned that using dictogloss to teach descriptive writing to students aids the entire writing process, some (33%) also agreed with it. However, only one student 5% remained neutral, 5% disagreed with it and 5% strongly disagreed with it. For Q.7, most of the students (48%) agreed and many (33%) strongly agreed that dictogloss helped them to understand the structure of descriptive writing. In contrast with it, 15% students remained neutral whereas only one student i.e 15% disagreed with the statement. In response to Q.8, most of the students strongly agreed (61%) and some (33%) agreed, that using dictogloss in writing class has helped in boosting their confidence to produce a text in English. Opposite to it, only one student i.e 5% disagreed with it. A large number of students (95%) strongly agreed and 5% agreed with the statement of Q.8. They enjoyed learning writing skills through dictogloss and hold an opinion that all the activities in dictogloss are full of fun. All the students who learnt writing skills through dictogloss strongly agreed (90%) and agreed (10) and stated that they want to continue learning through dictogloss.

Keeping in mind the perceptions and attitudes of students regarding the implementation of dictogloss technique in order to teach writing skills to the students, it can be interpreted that dictogloss is very effective in

motivating and boosting the confidence of the students to practice writing skills, aiding the entire teaching and learning process, the steps are easy to be understood and followed by students, it enables the students to use vocabulary and phrases in their written text, all the students enjoyed the activities and wished to continue learning through dictogloss. Therefore, it can be stated that dictogloss is a very effective teaching technique integrated with fun and enjoyment. It helps reduce the pressure, anxiety and boredom of the students in writing class.

5.2 Correlation Between Comprehending the Steps of Dictogloss and Students' Ability to Use Words and Phrases in their Descriptive Writing

Table 2

		The steps in dictogloss are understandable	I can use the words and phrases to do descriptive writing through dictogloss
The steps in dictogloss are understandable	Pearson Correlation	1	.568**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.007
	N	21	21
I can use the words and phrases to do descriptive writing through dictogloss	Pearson Correlation	.568**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.007	
	N	21	21

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Furthermore, the results of the Pearson correlation analyzed by using SPSS software i.e 0.01 level (2-tailed) show a significant correlation between understanding the steps of dictogloss and the students' ability to use words and phrases introduced through dictogloss techniques. Therefore, it can be said that due to the presence of simple activities in dictogloss, the students feel it easy to comprehend the vocabulary items, which in turn aids the entire writing process. If the activity is easy to understand and perform by students, it encourages and motivates them to participate, follow the instructions and perform the activities with fun.

5.3 Analysis of Pre- Test and Post- Test of Control Group

Table 3
Paired Samples Statistics

	Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Pre test of control group	67.25	20	10.809	2.417
Post test of control group	67.05	20	10.635	2.378

Table 4

Paired Samples Correlations

	N	Correlation	Sig.
Pre-test of control group & Post-test of control group	20	.980	.000

Table 5

Paired Samples Test

		Paired Differences					t
		Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference		
					Lower	Upper	
Pair 1	Pre-test of control group – Post-test of control group	.200	2.142	.479	-.803	1.203	.418

Table 6**Paired Samples Test**

		df	Sig. (2-tailed)
Pair 1	Pre test of control group - Post test of control group	19	.681

Table 4 shows that the correlation between pretest and post-test of control group is .98 with a strong significance of .000. Table 5 depicts that the standard deviation between the two tests of control group is 2.142 and mean is .200. However, the comparative results of paired sample test in Table 6 shows that the difference between the results of both the pre-test and post-test of control group is only 19 with significance of .681. It shows that there was no significant change in the results of the writing skills of students of control group by teaching them writing skills with a daily routine teaching methodology instead of dictogloss.

5.4 Analysis of Pre -Test and Post -Test of Experimental Group

Table 7**Paired Samples Statistics**

		Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Pair 1	Pre test of experimental group	68.24	21	13.015	2.840
	Post test of experimental group	75.71	21	12.815	2.796

Table 8**Paired Samples Correlations**

		N	Correlation	Sig.
Pair 1	Pre test of experimental group & Post test of experimental group	21	.940	.000

Table 9**Paired Samples Test**

		Paired Differences					t
		Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference		
					Lower	Upper	

Pre test of experimental group - Post test of experimental group	-7.476	4.490	.980	-9.520	-5.432	-7.630
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Table 10

Paired Samples Test

		df	Sig. (2-tailed)
Pair 1	Pre-test of experimental group – Post-test of experimental group	20	.000

Table 8 shows that the correlation between pretest and post-test of control group is .94 with a strong significance of .000. Table 9 depicts that the standard deviation between the two tests of control group is 4.490 and mean is -7.476. However, the comparative result of paired sample test in shown in table 10 shows that the difference between the results of both the pre-test and post-test of control group is 20 with a high significance of .000.

This shows that dictogloss teaching strategy that was employed to teach writing skills to the students of experimental group showed positive impact on the students' writing skills of students as they scored higher marks in their post-tests as compared to their pretest. Dictogloss played a vital role in enhancing the descriptive writing skills of the students at BS level which provides answer of our first research objective. The statistical analysis further shows a clear difference between the mean scores of post- tests of control- group (.200) with a standard deviation of 2.142 and experimental group (- 7.476) with standard deviation 4.490. The comparative results of the pretest and post- test of experimental group showed a prominent difference of 20 along with a high rate of significance of .000 which was 19 in the case of control group with .681 significance. The current findings are similar to the findings previous researches.

6 Discussion

It is evident from the comparative statistical analysis and interpretation of the results of pretest and post-tests of experimental and control group that dictogloss has a positive impact on students' writing skills. A number of underpinning actors have been uncovered from the responses of the students recorded through survey questionnaire.

6.1 Dictogloss is Easy and Integrates Writing with Fun

Dictogloss has remained an effective strategy suggested by (Younis, Bataineh & Yarmouk, 2016; Joe, 2022) which motivates the students to practice writing skills. As employed by Sani, Inderawati & Vianty (2016), podcast was used to conduct dictogloss in ESL class. The easy steps used in dictogloss facilitate the entire teaching and learning process. The result of the correlation between understanding the steps of dictogloss and ability to use words and phrases in writing depicted that because the students understood each step, they listened to the podcast with concentration and interest, understood the vocabulary items used in context, enabled them to use the new vocabulary items in their written work. It can be said that as dictogloss introduces the new words and phrases in context which enables the students to grasp them more easily and with fun. As declared by Lim and Jacobs (2001) that by doing dictogloss the students achieved inner satisfaction and fun

In the regular methods of teaching writing skills, the students are unable to understand the contextual use of vocabulary items as they are introduced in isolation. Due to the lack of lack activities in writing class, the student takes writing activities as a burden for them. It is evident from this research as Lim and Jacobs (2001) that the activities like dictogloss which help students learn the language in context and with fun make the entire process easy which help them to understand the organization and mechanics, develops the interest of the students, integrates writing with fun, motivate them to do practice and improve their concentration. Therefore,

the students showed their wish to keep learning through dictogloss. Moreover, the repetition of podcast in dictogloss further helped to reduce the stress and worry of students regarding the fear of missing out the chunks of listening from the podcast. This made the complete activity full of fun and entertainment. Students totally ignored the factor of learning writing skills rather they learnt writing skills incorporated with fun and joy.

6.2 Role of Dictogloss to improve Students' Confidence

Dictogloss, being a collaborative teaching and learning strategy, contributes to improve overall confidence of students. After listening to the podcast, students focus on the usage of words and phrases and a group discussion was held. The students shared their work with each other and discussed the ideas they listened in the podcast. This created a complete language learning environment in class, the students got the opportunity to practice speaking skills, get encouraged to share their work as well as the ideas and learn through collaboration. It further encouraged the concept of team work and get benefit from each other. This collaborative environment reduced the stress of learning a foreign language and also reduced the fear of producing a written task in isolation. They felt togetherness and facilitated each other throughout. It can be depicted that dictogloss not only promotes learning English language in context but also cancelled the concept of learning to write in isolation. It promoted language leaning in a language learning environment. Encouraged friendship, mutual support in the writing class. The students not only boost their overall confidence but also feel motivated to learn a language, orally practice a language, open up and share their ideas and produce a written text with each other's support. It promoted sharing and caring and reduced the concept of loneliness, selfishness and jealousy. The students helped each other to improve their performance. It promoted an atmosphere of healthy comparison and criticism.

6.3 Critical Thinking Skill

Teaching and learning through dictogloss helps to develop critical thinking skills of students. They listened to the podcast, tried to contextual understand the new words and phrases and got prepared to the collaborative writing task. They tried to use maximum time to critically listen to the podcast, prepare the list of words and phrases introduced in the podcast. During the small group activity, the students compared their list with the list of other group members, also shared their work with members of other groups, critically noted what was incorrect and missing in each other's work. Moreover, as they produced the written work as a group activity, they did peer checking of each other's work. During the peer checking they pointed out each other's mistakes and helped each other do correction. All these small collaborative activities, promoted critical thinking and analytical skills of the students similar to findings presented by Wajnryb (1990) and learn English by critically analyzing each other's mistakes and guiding one another in doing corrections. They also learnt how to work as a team (Vasiljevic, 2010), provide healthy and constructive feedback to their mates. In the end, it can be said that dictogloss promoted team work spirit as well as critical thinking skills of students. It encouraged criticism for the sake of improvement rather than criticism for the sake of criticism. Also improved tolerance to listen to positive criticism and follow the instructions.

6.4 Dictogloss helps integrate all four language skills in writing class

- The use of podcast in the writing class as used by Sani, Inderawati & Vianty (2016), condemns the boring concept of teaching writing as an isolated skill. Further, it promotes the integration of not only listening with writing but also provides opportunities of conducting speaking activities in the writing class. These findings are in congruence with the findings of Sani, Inderawati & Vianty (2016) who studied the impact of dictogloss on listening as well as writing skills of students. Students practice target language in the form of small group discussions, class discussion, sharing vocabulary and ideas with each other, checking each other's work through reading and pointing out mistakes, thinking about possible remedies of the problems and providing feedback to their fellow students by using target language. In addition to that the oral presentations of the students in the end of the entire activity also provided a full opportunity to the students to improve their self-confidence by giving oral presentations in front of the whole class. Besides this, the rest of the students listen to the presenters which develops their interest and helps them to enhance their listening skills (Sani, Inderawati & Vianty (2016)). No doubt, all steps and activities included in dictogloss provided a platform to integrate and practice all four language skills, researchers such as Jose (2022), Kurtaj (2021) and Vasiljevic (2010) also supported teaching English through integration of all four language skills. All language skills in English facilitate acquisition of other language skills. The students gain more grammatical accuracy through dictogloss (Kurtaj, 2021). It is evident that integration of writing skill with listening, speaking and reading, not only helped develop writing skills of the students but also helped students improve their other language skills (Joe, 2021). Hence, improvement in all language skills exhibited an overall improvement in English language skills of students. Therefore, ESL teacher must not solely rely on traditional method in ESL writing class (Jose 2022; Younis, Bataineh & Yarmouk, 2016) and rather

they are strongly suggested to more frequently use innovative teaching methods. ESL teachers should use an eclectic teaching approach to break the monotony in ESL class.

Conclusion

The focus of this research was to explore the effectiveness of dictogloss teaching strategy on writing skills of the students at undergraduate, to investigate students' perceptions and attitudes towards learning through dictogloss and to find whether there is any correlation between comprehending the steps of dictogloss and ability to use the vocabulary items introduced through dictogloss and in their written work. The effectiveness of dictogloss technique to improve writing skills of students is clearly evident from the high scores obtained by students of experimental group. Moreover, the difference between mean, standard deviation and difference between the results of pretest and post test also support the statement that dictogloss is a very useful technique to teach writing skills to the students of ELT which fulfills the first objective of our research paper. The statistical results of the gathered from students of experimental group after being taught by dictogloss provides strong evidences that students have a very positive attitude towards learning writing skills through dictogloss, they felt motivated, encourages to write. Moreover, the students perceived dictogloss as a useful strategy which makes the entire process of learning writing skills easy and full of fun and entertainment. They wish to continue learning through. The findings also show that there is a strong correlation between comprehending the steps of dictogloss and students' ability to use new vocabulary items in their writing. To end up it can be said that the integration of fun with activity, collaborative learning class environment, integration of all four skills in writing class, easy fun based small activities in dictogloss played a crucial role in making dictogloss an effective strategy to teach writing skills to the students.

Recommendation

According to the results, findings and interpretation, dictogloss teaching techniques has been highly recommended by the researcher.

- English language teachers of new era must cease teaching writing skills in a strict, stressful and authoritative teaching and learning environment and try to integrate fun in writing class to wither away the boredom and anxiety in writing class
- ELT teachers must develop a collaborative learning environment in the class by utilizing innovative teaching strategies such as dictogloss. The students get benefit from the strengths and abilities of their fellow mates.
- The job of ELT teachers is not only to develop writing skills but being teachers of the students of 20th century, they must inculcate team spirit, tolerance, critical thinking skills, learning grammar in context, ability to criticize for the sake of improvement, pull up each other as per their own abilities, remove jealousy among students, feel happiness in success of their fellow students, start believing in win- win principal inside as well as outside classroom.
- ELT teachers must explore the likes and dislikes of their students regarding teaching and learning in the class. If the students show their likelihood regarding a certain teaching strategy, they will take interest, find it easy to use which will in turn positively impact the entire teaching and learning process.
- ELT teachers must include dictogloss as part of their routine and frequently use it due to its effectiveness, fun, collaborative learning activities, learning language in context and ability to integrate all four English language skills in class.
- More wide scale as well as small scale research studies are recommended using a variety of variables such as students' proficiency level, gender and their learning styles on both writing as well as other language skills in Pakistan as well as other parts of the world

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